

ISic3079

I.Sicily inscription 3079

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Ietas

Place of origin (modern)

Monte Iato

Provenance

Found in the East necropolis (located in grid squares IKL/37-39 on plan in AK 22 (1979), p.59 abb.1)

Coordinates

37.966821, 13.209082

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Monte Iato, Antiquarium Case d'Alia e parco archeologico Monte Iato

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate epsilon

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Δ]έκο

2. με χαῖ

3. ρε

Apparatus

Text after Isler 1988

Translation (en)

Farewell Dekomos

Commentary

Dekomos is presumably Decimus, and is attested in other Sicilian greek inscriptions, such as ISic2952 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic2952>]

(Cefalu), and as Dekomia at Syracuse in ISic0841 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0841>]

Digital identifiers:

TM 645431

EDCS 64400373

PHI 331802

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 38.0932

Isler, H. P. 1988. Grabungen auf dem Monte Iato 1987. *Antike Kunst*. 31: 21-24. At 23-24 tav.4.5

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